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Ms. P. Suganthi is a Textile & Management professional over 11 years of comprehensive experience in Textile production, Textile Research and Management Education. She holds a B. Tech degree in Textile Technology, P. G Diploma in Apparel Production and Management, MBA and pursuing her Phd in Operations and Management. She is currently working as an Assistant Professor in School of Management, Sri Krishna College of Engineering and Technology.

Her specializations include

- Production Management
- Quality and Quality Control
- NABL Audit and Documentation
- Co-authored books on Quality Norms, trends in cotton, research articles on medical textiles.
- Project coordinator for various projects like Quality update on sewing thread, Calibration cotton etc.

She is a member of QCFI, organised 10th National conclave, presented papers and developed case studies in National and International Conferences. She has 8 + years' experience at SITRA with wide expertise on fibre, yarn, fabric testing and knitting and weaving Department. She has also trained national and international candidates on textiles. She had undergone training programs on Proficiency testing (NABL), research study selections and statistical calculations. She also coauthored research paper on "Poisson's Ratio of Non-Woven Spun Bonded Fabric for Medical Apparel" in medical textiles, published in international journal (A1) TEKSTİL VE KONFEKSİYON. Apart from all above she also has implemented TQM work methods, Production planning and control at Cheslind Textiles India Pvt. Ltd. during her tenure.

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Readiness of SMEs in the Indian Textile Industry to Embrace ESG Practices

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Introduction

ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) considerations have rapidly ascended to the forefront of global investment priorities. ESG ranks top five for business performance beyond financial metrics. This trend is partly driven by the United Nations' Climate Action initiatives aimed at achieving Net-Zero emissions, coupled with ambitious environmental targets set by nations worldwide.

In 2020, the European Union took a significant step by drafting regulations that require companies to disclose their performance against ESG benchmarks, signaling a move towards transparency and accountability in corporate practices. The textile industry, known for its substantial environmental footprint, is at a critical juncture where integrating ESG principles into its operations mitigate its ecological impact and also enhance its competitiveness in the global market. This article investigates the critical role of ESG in transforming the textile industry, emphasizing the necessity of adopting sustainable practices that align with global sustainability goals, consumer expectations for ethical and responsible production and challenges.

World Indexes

The World Economics ESG methodology developed a composite index based on the average of three indexes: (i) Environmental Factors, (ii) Social Factors, and (iii) Governance Factors. The index is based on a scale of 0-100, where a higher score indicates better resilience towards ESG. According to their data, India scores 60.6 (Grade E) on Environmental Impact, 51.3 on Social Impact (Grade D), and 47.2 on Governance Impact (Grade C).

ESG in Textile Industry

The textile industry process includes fiber production, cleaning, yarn manufacturing, knitting or weaving, dyeing, and garmenting & packaging. Natural fibers are cultivated from farmland and processed, while synthetic fibers. Regenerated fibres involve harmful chemical processing. The conversion process from fiber to fabric consumes significant natural resources, leaves carbon footprints, and creates pollution of air, water, and land.

According to the World Bank, the fashion industry accounts for 10% of global carbon emissions annually and is the fourth highest category for resource and water consumption. The industry uses around 215 trillion liters of water each year, contributing to water pollution with chemicals, cleansing agents, and microfibers. Social concerns within the textile industry include working hours, diversity in leadership, fair wages, job security, discrimination, safe working conditions, and supply chain management. These factors underscore the necessity of considering environmental and social impacts when formulating and executing mitigation strategies.

ESG in the International Scenario - US & Europe

The US aims for a net-zero target by 2050, and the New York State legislature is deliberating on the Fashion Sustainability and Social Accountability Act. This bill mandates clothing companies earning over \$100 million in annual revenue to outline and disclose their supply chains and environmental impact. These

companies must establish emissions reduction targets based on scientific standards. This disclosure impacts the textile industry of importing nations like India and Bangladesh if ESG compliance is ignored. The textile industry contributes significantly to global environmental challenges, accounting for 8-10% of humanity's carbon emissions.

Europe has emerged as a leader in implementing policies and strategies for sustainable fashion. In 2021, France enacted legislation imposing new requirements on the fashion industry concerning waste prevention, materials reuse, and accountability for environmental claims. The 2023 ESG fashion agenda is anticipated to reshape industry norms and catalyse substantial change, positioning the fashion sector as a crucial participant in the global sustainability movement.

Gearing up with the Global ESG Requirement

Amidst the rising global significance of ESG considerations, the Indian textile sector must meet ESG criteria, particularly in anticipation of forthcoming sustainability mandates from the EU. Given Europe's substantial contribution to India's apparel exports, Indian exporters face pressure to swiftly adjust their practices to adhere to ESG standards, ensuring their competitiveness and continued access to this critical market.

Steps Taken by the Central Government for ESG

At the COP26-Glasgow summit, Prime Minister Narendra Modi pledged to set a net-zero target by 2070. The Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) has introduced Business Responsibility and Sustainability Report (BRSR) guidelines, mandating ESG disclosure from the current financial year. Additionally, SEBI established an ESG advisory committee in May 2022 to enhance BRSR requirements and streamline ESG ratings and investing. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) issued guidelines in February 2023, encompassing acceptance of green deposits, a disclosure framework on climate-related financial risks, and guidance on climate scenario analysis and stress testing.

Challenges Faced in Implementation of ESG

Medium and Small-Scale Sectors (MSME) and small-scale textile industries are already in financial crisis due to rising cotton prices and electricity charges. Several industries have downscaled operations or closed due to the impact of COVID-19 and rising cotton prices. The awareness of ESG concepts is limited, and small-scale sectors are mostly Scope 3 suppliers, which complicates comprehensive reporting efforts.

Key areas requiring improvement include transparency in raw material sustainability declarations, equitable treatment and statutory benefits for migrant laborers, and ensuring safe working conditions for all workers. Additionally, achieving gender pay parity, enhancing water and waste management, transitioning to renewable energy sources, and adhering to pollution control norms for fly, fluff, and sound pollution are crucial. The industry must also focus on comprehensive effluent treatment, ensuring organic cotton sustainability, improving accident reporting, and complying with safety regulations.

Moreover, significant investments in renewable energy, water consumption management, and implementation of checkpoints to ensure sustainability across business processes are essential for long-term viability. Addressing these ESG-related issues will not only help the textile sector meet global sustainability mandates but also enhance its competitiveness and market positioning in the international arena.

Conclusion

Integrating ESG principles in the textile industry (SME's) is vital for mitigating environmental impacts and ensuring social responsibility. Aligning with global sustainability goals and consumer expectations, particularly in the face of emerging regulations, is crucial for maintaining competitiveness. Addressing challenges through comprehensive reporting, investment in sustainable practices, and adherence to stringent standards will enhance the industry's resilience and market position.

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